

INNOVATIVE METHODS IN READING: HOW MOTIVATION SHAPES UNDERSTANDING

Mirzamakhmudova Iroda

Under the supervision of **D.S.Khayrullayeva**
Uzbekistan State World Languages University
mirzamaxmudovairoda@gmail.com

Abstract: *This article explores the essential role of motivation in reading comprehension. Reading is not merely the act of recognizing words but a higher-order cognitive process involving decoding, understanding, and reasoning. The study examines different types of reading, factors that decrease motivation, and effective solutions to inspire and sustain reading habits. It also highlights practical methods to enhance the reading experience and improve comprehension through motivational and cognitive techniques.*

Keywords: *Reading, motivation, comprehension, intensive reading, extensive reading, skimming, scanning, cognitive process, distraction, goal setting, active recall, spaced repetition, pomodoro technique, rewarding, learning environment.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola o'qishni tushunishda motivatsiyaning muhim rolini tahlil qiladi. O'qish nafaqat so'zlarni tanib olish harakati, balki dekodlash, tushunish va fikrlashni o'z ichiga olgan yuqori darajadagi kognitiv jarayon ekanligini ilgari suradi. Maqolada turli xil o'qish turlari, motivatsiyani kamaytiradigan omillar va o'qish odatlarini ilhomlantirish hamda qo'llab-quvvatlash uchun samarali yechimlar tahlil etilgan. Shuningdek, ushbu maqola motivatsion va kognitiv usullar orqali o'qish tajribasini oshirish va tushunishni yaxshilashning amaliy usullarini ta'kidlaydi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *O'qish, motivatsiya, tushunish, intensiv o'qish, ekstensiv o'qish, tez o'qish (skimming), ma'lumot izlash (scanning), kognitiv jarayon, chalg'ituvchi omillar, maqsad qo'yish, faol takrorlash, oraliqli takrorlash, pomodoro usuli, o'zingni mukofotlash, o'qish muhiti.*

Аннотация: *Эта статья анализирует важную роль мотивации в понимании прочитанного. В ней утверждается, что чтение — это не просто распознавание слов, а сложный когнитивный процесс, включающий декодирование, понимание и осмысление. В статье рассматриваются различные виды чтения, факторы, снижающие мотивацию, а также эффективные решения для вдохновения и поддержки привычки к чтению. Кроме того, подчеркиваются практические способы улучшения читательского опыта и понимания текста с помощью мотивационных и когнитивных подходов.*

Ключевые слова: *Чтение, Мотивация, Понимание, Интенсивное чтение, Экстенсивное чтение, Просматривание (skimming), Поиск информации (scanning), Когнитивный процесс, Отвлекающие факторы, Постановка целей,*

Активное повторение, Интервальное повторение, Метод Помодоро, Самопоощрение, Среда для чтения.

Introduction

The most basic level of reading involves recognition of words. Recognising the very simple letters and words is the fundamental understanding of reading. Reading is a complex cognitive skill that allows people to gain knowledge from written language. This process includes decoding written symbols, connecting them to sounds and meaning, and comprehending the overall message of the text. In turn, this requires attention, memory, perception, and reasoning, which are the key components of cognition. Hence, reading is not considered as a simple mechanical activity, but a higher-order cognitive process.

Reading is a key skill that can have a crucial role not only in individuals' personal lives, but also in their academic successes as it can enhance comprehension, expand vocabulary as well as stimulate critical thinking. There are main four kinds of reading: intensive reading, extensive reading, skimming and scanning.

In intensive reading, readers read short detailed texts to understand every aspect, focusing on comprehension, vocabulary, and grammar. In extensive reading, people read longer texts for joy, pleasure and to gain general understanding, rather than focusing on minute details. Skimming is reading a text quickly to get the general idea by focusing on headings and introductory sentences. Scanning, however, is searching for a piece of information, such as a name, date or statistic, without reading the whole text.

There are several factors why most people have no passion to study books, including lack of interest, distractions, difficulties in understanding, and struggling with setting clear goals. Many individuals read books which are not their type, and as a result they can end up with demotivation to study more.

Since we are living in the era of surrounded technologies, such as mobile phones, laptops and different social media websites, people can get easily distracted by seeing notifications on their phones. Another reason is that sometimes some students find reading theoretical materials too hard and give up instead of trying.

Given that most people have not set clear professional goals—such as a future career, self-improvement, or exams—they lack guidance and direction. Consequently, they don't feel the urge to read books in order to acquire more knowledge.

There are several methods for people to improve their motivation to read books. Creating a desired atmosphere is one of the most needed things because the environment has a crucial influence on individuals' reading habits. For example, some readers prefer silence and serene atmosphere, while others can focus better with background music or sitting at their favourite café. Secondly, it is better to minimise

distractions while reading a book. People can turn off their mobile phones and use website blockers to limit social media access during study sessions.

Another solution is rewarding yourself. Celebrating small achievements creates a strong willingness to read more and more. Only giving sweets or letting yourself watch a movie after reading one chapter can boost your desire towards reading.

Using effective methods can make the reading process more intriguing and interactive for a reader. These methods involve active recall, spaced repetition, teaching others and pomodoro techniques.

In active recall technique, after reading, a reader can actively test himself by answering practice questions and quizzes, or using flashcards.

Spaced repetition is based on reviewing the information at increasing intervals over time to move information from short-term to long-term memory.

Teaching others also helps readers to increase their understanding as they try to organise thoughts and explain them clearly.

Finally, in pomodoro technique, people read a book for 25 minutes, and then take a 5-minute short break. This can prevent them from getting fed up with reading very easily.

Conclusion

Motivation is the key factor to improve reading comprehension. By understanding the reading types, analysing the reasons why students avoid reading, and applying solutions, students can make better results.

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